

Weddell Sea Observatory of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Change – WOBEC Standard Operating Procedures

Technical Documentation

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Versions

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Method responsible: Sebastien Moreau/Jacqueline Stefels

1 Description of sampling gear

Water column structure is sampled with the CTD-rosette ~~installed aboard R/V Polarstern~~, which is equipped with a temperature and conductivity sensor, a pressure sensor, oxygen and fluorescence sensors, and an altimeter, among others.

Processing of several samples taken from the CTD-rosette will include chemical use. A list of the necessary chemicals and their corresponding parameter is provided below. It is the responsibility of the individual using the chemical and processing the sample to operate in a manner that is safe for themselves, others on the ship, and the environment being sampled. Safety Data Sheets (SDS) should be readily available in the labs and proper chemical storage systems should be decided on and implemented before the cruise, including locked chemical storage cabinets and designated workspaces for radioisotopes.

Chemical	Parameter	Safety consideration
Saturated mercury chloride (HgCl ₂)	DIC and CH ₄	Highly toxic
Methanol	Chlorophyll a	Carcinogenic
Glutaraldehyde	Taxonomy and flow cytometry	Carcinogenic
Formaldehyde	Taxonomy	Carcinogenic and mutagenic
Hydrochloric acid (HCl)	Several	Corrosive
Ethanol	Several	Toxic
NaOH	DMSP	Corrosive

2 Sampling gear deployment

2.1 Deployment

Deployment should follow typical routines aboard R/V Polarstern. Here we provide a few points from deployment routines aboard R/V Kronprins Haakon.

1. Start data acquisition just before the CTD leaves deck to help with assessing surface pressure adjustment
2. Soak for 1 minute at 5 m (10 m if very cold and there is a risk of freezing during deployment/deck sampling), bring back up to surface (just submerged) and leave there for 3 minutes before lowering to max depth. Rest at max depth for at least 1 minute

3. Lower speed should be between 0.8 and 1 m s⁻¹ and if LADCP is mounted lowering speed should be reduced to 0.7 m s⁻¹
4. Water sampling should be taken at standard depths that are pre-determined before deployment, that is except for the depth of the maximum CHl-a which is determined in real time. Niskin bottles are closed on the upcast by stopping the CTD at desired depth and waiting for at least one minute before firing the bottle.
5. Stop data acquisition when the CTD is back on deck.

2.2 Calibration

Annual calibration of all CTD sensors should be documented and samples for calibration of conductivity cell(s) should be taken regularly throughout the cruise.

2.3 Post-Deployment

Postprocessing should follow standard routines aboard R/V Polarstern with raw data available and accessible for postprocessing by individual researchers. Metadata of the cast should be recorded in the CTD file and on the CTD sampling sheet. A sampling log sheet should be used for overview of type of water sample taken and sample number. The order of the samples on the CTD log sheet should reflect the order in which samples should be taken from the Niskin-rosette. Below is a suggested ordering of sampling from a ship CTD taken from the Norwegian Polar Institute 2024 Arctic Ocean cruise.

1. Methane
2. DIC/AT
3. DMSP
4. Stable oxygen isotopes
5. Inorganic nutrients
6. CDOM
7. Particle absorption
8. TSM
9. Chlorophyll *a* and phaeopigments
10. POC/PON
11. FCM
12. Phytoplankton taxonomy
13. Salinity

2.4 Common Issues

Well organized and intuitive log sheets and labeling systems should be used commonly throughout the cruise. Water sampling budgets should be agreed on well before deployment and sampling order should be made clear before the Rosette is back on deck.

Vinyl gloves (not nitrile) should be used during sampling and readily available in the CTD hanger.

3 Sample sorting-collection-preservation procedure: Water samples from Niskin bottles

Water samples taken from the ship's Niskin bottles are described below in separate sub-chapters.

3.1 Salinity samples

- Rinse bottle and bottle cap three times.
- Dry off bottle neck and cap with paper towel before closing the bottle.
- Remember to place plastic insert before closing the cap. Pay special attention to threads on the bottle and in the cap when screwing close.
- Note down cast number/station number, Niskin bottle number and sample bottle number on the sampling log.

3.2 Dissolved inorganic carbon / total alkalinity

- Total DIC measures the sum of bicarbonate, carbonate, carbonic acid and dissolved CO₂ in seawater.
- Use a tube to gently fill a 250 mL borosilicate bottle directly from the Niskin bottle. Take care to avoid air bubbles in the tubing.
- Overfill sampling bottle 1-2 volumes for rinsing and removal of air bubbles. Carefully remove the tubing out of the bottle and close the cap. Some headspace (a few mL) is okay.
- After all bottles have been filled, add 60 µL saturated mercuric chloride (HgCl₂) to each sample by submerging the pipette tip into the sample. Close the bottle with the blue cap. Do not shake or mix.
- Store samples in a cool and dark place. Do not freeze.

3.3 Oxygen isotope ratios ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$)

- Ratios of ¹⁶O to ¹⁸O ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$) in the H₂O molecule are measured to a very high accuracy. Samples of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ are collected to determine the fractions of river water and sea-ice meltwater in the ocean. This sample is not related to dissolved oxygen.
- Sample rinse a 20 mL glass scintillation vial and cap three times.
- Fill the vial with seawater directly from the Niskin creating a convex meniscus.

- Carefully apply the cap and check for small air bubble.
- When all $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ samples have been collected, dry the vials, tighten the caps and seal with Parafilm.
- Store $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ samples at room temperature or in a fridge, avoid freezing.

3.4 Methane

- Methane is a volatile and relatively insoluble trace gas and the concentration in the sample will be affected by prolonged contact with air. Therefore, it should be sampled immediately after retrieval of the rosette.
- Attach a flexible silicone sampling tube (about 30 cm long) to the Niskin bottle and flush the tube with sample to expel all air bubbles.
- Rinse a 160 mL serum bottle with sample water then place the end of the tube at the bottom of the bottle. Allow the bottle to overflow by at least two volumes.
- Slowly withdraw the tubing from the bottle and reduce flow towards the neck of the bottle by pinching the tube. The bottle should be completely full, free of bubbles, and have a slightly convex meniscus over the opening.
- Immediately add 50 μL saturated mercuric chloride (HgCl_2), then seal the bottle with a metal seal and butyl rubber septum using the crimping tool.
- Store the samples in a cool, dark place (refrigeration at +4C).
- Rinse crimping tool in freshwater after sampling.

3.5 Inorganic nutrients

- Set up a clean working space and use vinyl gloves. Acid wash sampling vials (20 mL scintillation vials), syringes, and swinnex before sampling. Rinse sampling vials, syringes, and swinnex with MiliQ after acid bath and before use.
- Assemble a swinnex with a pre-combusted GF/F filter. Place syringe into undiluted melt (chemistry core) and take up a small amount of sample to rinse the syringe. Repeat three times.
- Take up a full syringe of sample (about 60 mL), push out air, and attach swinnex. Using steady but light pressure, gently push sample through the filter at a drip-drip-drip speed. Rinse the filter with sample, and then rinse the sampling vial and cap with filtered sample 3 times.
- Fill sampling vial with filtered sample, leaving a small amount of headspace for freezing.
- Store samples at -20C.

3.6 Particulate organic carbon / nitrogen and their stable isotopic $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ compositions.

- Rinse a 2 L clear plastic bottle with sample three times using seawater directly from the Niskin.
- Completely fill sample bottle and take to the lab for filtration.
- Filter up to 2 L of sample (depending on particle concentration) onto pre-combusted 25 mm GF/F filters. Filters should be combusted at 450C for 12 hours before the cruise. Remember to gently mix the bottle before filtering to ensure that particles are suspended. Also ensure that the mesh side of the filter is facing up on the filter holder, not the soft waves side (back side).
- Filter under low vacuum pressure (about -30 kPa) and cover the funnels with aluminum foil when filtering. Rinse the funnel with filtered seawater once the sample has been filtered. Take care not to let the filters dry out.
- After filtration, use forceps to carefully place GF/F into Pall filter slides. Place slides into oven set at 60C and allow them to fully dry (about 24 hours).
- Store samples at room temperature. Wrap together filter slides from one station in aluminum foil and keep them in a labelled Ziploc bag.
- Prepare a reference filter (blank) for each station by filtering filtered seawater onto a pre-combusted filter. The reference filter will get a normal running number, so make sure to make a note on the CTD log sheet to avoid confusion with numbering on following casts.

3.7 Chlorophyll *a*

- Rinse a 1 L brown plastic bottle with sample three times using seawater directly from the Niskin. Chl *a* is light sensitive, so keep samples in the dark as much as possible.
- Completely fill sample bottle and take it to the lab for filtration/extraction.
- Filter up to 1 L of sample depending on biomass (a light color on the filter is enough) onto 25 mm GF/F filters. Remember to gently mix the bottle before filtering to ensure that particles are suspended. Also ensure that the mesh side of the filter is facing up on the filter holder, not the soft waves side (back side).
- Filter under low vacuum pressure (about -30 kPa) and cover the funnels with aluminum foil when filtering. Rinse the funnel with filtered seawater once the sample has been filtered. Take care not to let the filters dry out.
- Use forceps to lift the filters into plastic tubes for extraction.
- Add 5 mL of methanol to the extraction tubes, close with lid, and cover with aluminum foil to block light. Place in refrigerator (dark, +4°C).

- Allow pigments to extract into methanol for 12-24 hours, making sure to note the start and end time of extraction.
- Rinse filtration funnels and manifold with freshwater between stations.

3.8 Biogenic silica

- Rinse a 1 L plastic bottle with sample three times using seawater directly from the Niskin.
- Filter up to 1 L (depending on diatom biomass present) onto a polycarbonate membrane filter (0.8 μm pore size, 25 mm diameter) under low vacuum pressure (-30 kpa).
- Place filter into pre-labeled plastic petri dish and place in oven at +60°C to dry, leaving petri dish slightly open to allow for evaporation.
- Once filters are dry (ca. 24 hours in the oven), seal petri dishes with parafilm and wrap filter slides from one station together in aluminum foil. Place in labelled Ziploc bag and store at room temperature.
- Prepare a reference filter (blank) for each sampling event by filtering a similar volume of filtered seawater onto a filter and treating it the same as the samples.

3.9 Phytoplankton taxonomy

- Fill 190 mL of sample directly from Niskin bottle into a measuring cylinder. Sample rinse cylinder before filling.
- Decant 190 mL sample into a pre-labelled brown glass (or plastic) bottle).
- Bring samples back to the lab for fixation with aldehyde mixture under the fume hood. Add 0.8 mL of 25% glutaraldehyde and allow to fix for approx. 5 min. Thereafter add 10 mL of 20% hexamine-buffered formaldehyde. The final concentration is 0.1% glutaraldehyde and 1% formaldehyde in a 200 mL solution.
- Store the samples in cool, dark conditions. Do not freeze.

3.10 Flow cytometry

- Prepare for station by adding 38 μl of 25% glutaraldehyde into each pre-labeled 2 mL cryovials (3 per depth) under the fume hood.
- Using a syringe directly from the Niskin bottle, rinse a 50 mL falcon tube three times with sample filtered through a 40 μm cell strainer. Then fill the falcon tube with about 40 mL of filtered sample.
- Take samples back to the lab and pipette 1.8 mL of filtered sample into the prepared cryovials.
- Fix the samples for 2 hours in the fridge and then snap freeze in -80°C. Store samples in cryobox at -80°C.

3.11 Net community production using O₂ optodes

- Set up computer system, chambers, and water circulator on work bench. It is smart to divide the work bench into dry and wet areas as the electronic equipment must not get wet. Assess everything for damage and potential leaks and check computer system and probe life. Ensure everything is secure with tape and straps.
- Arrange LED lamp adjacent to clear wall on chamber.
- Arrange the clear bottles in the chamber and label consecutively from position one to position nine, with the first position marking the bottle closest to the light (i.e., the clear chamber wall). The bottle at position ten (farthest from the light) should be prepared with black electrical tape to prevent any light from entering in the bottle and will be used as the dark control.
- Add magnetic stir bars to each bottle.
- From the rosette on deck, collect the necessary volume of sample directly from the Nixsin bottle. Typically, two depths are chosen for oxygen optode incubations, such as surface (5 m) and the DCM. Remember to sample rinse the collection bottle 3 times before filling completely.
- Back in the lab, use a peristaltic pump with nitex covering the outflow to remove any large grazers to fill bottles with sample.
- Overfill bottles to prevent formation of a headspace. There must be no bubbles in the bottle once the stopper is placed.
- Cover the clear wall of the chamber with foil and place bottles into pre-cooled and darkened chamber for equilibration (2-3 hours minimum).
- Calibrate optode sensors immediately prior to each incubation using a 0% and 100% dissolved oxygen standards of 0.17 M sodium dithionite (Na₂S₂O₄) and air saturated water (bubbled FSW for more than 10 minutes), respectively. This accounts for any sensor drift or photodegradation that may have occurred with extended use. The calibration solutions should be made fresh before each incubation.
- Once calibrated and equilibrated, fit each bottle with an optode sensor, taking care not to pull the optodes up/down during place or incubation to avoid volume displacement and inaccurate measurements. Cover incubation with black garbage bags to protect from light.
- Incubate samples for 24-70 hours under continuous illumination and mixing. The 1 cm magnetic stir bars should be set to about 60 rpm. The oxygen concentration is recorded for each bottle at about 2 s time intervals throughout the entire incubation period.

- To stop incubation, turn off optodes and remove from bottles. Measure average PAR using handheld PAR sensor at each bottle position by replacing optodes with PAR probe.
- Pool all samples after incubation and filter for additional chlorophyll measurement. Rinse optodes with MilliQ and gently blot dry with Kim wipe to prevent salt damage and corrosion. Rinse incubation bottles with FSW after each incubation.

3.12 DMSP

- DMSP is a volatile and relatively insoluble trace gas and the concentration in the sample will be affected by prolonged contact with air. Therefore, it should be sampled immediately after retrieval of the rosette.
- Prelabel the sample bottles prior to sampling.
- Attach a flexible silicone sampling tube (about 30 cm long) to the Niskin bottle and flush the tube with sample to expel all air bubbles.
- Rinse a 70 mL amber serum bottle with sample water then place the end of the tube at the bottom of the bottle. Allow the bottle to overflow by at least two volumes.
- Slowly withdraw the tubing from the bottle and reduce flow towards the neck of the bottle by pinching the tube, making sure to avoid any bubble formation. The bottle should be completely full, free of bubbles, and have a slightly convex meniscus over the opening.
- Close the bottle and store in a coolbox, preferably filled with surface water.
- Take duplicate samples.

3.13 Net community production by recording uptake of the ^{13}C stable isotope.

- Collect 2L seawater in a 2L Nalgene bottle. Typically, two depths are chosen for incubations, such as surface (5 m) and the DCM. Remember to sample rinse the collection bottle 3 times before filling completely.
- Start the experiment by adding 2 ml ^{13}C - NaHCO_3 from a stock solution (1 gram ^{13}C - HCO_3 + 20 ml MQ)
- Mix the tracer by gently shaking the bottle. This is important!
- Take t_0 samples
- DIC: fill a 8ml amber bottle to the top. Store at 4°C.
- DMSP: use a 10ml pipet for 3 x 10ml in 20ml screw-top vials + 1 pellet NaOH. Store at -20°C.
- Chl.a: filter ca. 300ml; for further details see protocol
- From the Nalgene bottle, transfer 250ml to 6 tissue culture flasks.
- Arrange LED lamp adjacent to clear wall on chamber (see protocol for O₂ optodes.

- Arrange the tissue flasks and label consecutively from position one to position six, with the first position marking the bottle closest to the light (i.e., the clear chamber wall) in a pre-cooled and darkened chamber. The bottle at position six (farthest from the light) should be prepared with black electrical tape to prevent any light from entering in the bottle and will be used as the dark control.
- Incubate samples for 8-10 hours under continuous illumination. Gentle shake the flasks every hour
- To stop incubation, take the samples from the experiment in a fixed consecutive order for filtration. Make sure to note the time. Prepare and label alu foil before filtration.
- Depending on the biomass 50-200ml is filtered over 2.5cm pre-combusted GFF Whatman filters using a low vacuum pressure (-30 kpa) under dim light conditions. Fold the filter 1x, pack in alu foil and flash freeze in LN2.
- Store at -20°C
- Complete the meta-sheet.

4 Sample analysis method

4.1 Salinity samples

- Salinity samples should be analyzed using shipboard salinometer and used for calibration of conductivity cell(s) on CTD.

4.2 Dissolved inorganic carbon / total alkalinity

- Samples for DIC/TA should be stored and shipped to the Institute of Marine Research in Tromsø, Norway for analysis using potentiometric titration with 0.1N hydrochloric acid on a Versatile Instrument for the Determination of Titration Alkalinity (VINDTA 3D, Marianda, Germany).

4.3 Stable oxygen isotopes

- Samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ should be stored and shipped to Vrije Universiteit, Brussels, Belgium for analysis on a Perspective isotope ratio mass spectrometer (Nu Instrument, Ametek) coupled to a Gas Bench system. All samples should also be standardized against V-SMOW.

4.4 Methane

- Samples for methane should be stored and shipped to the University of Liege, Belgium for analysis with a gas chromatographer.

4.5 Inorganic nutrients

- Samples for inorganic nutrients should be stored and shipped to UiT the Arctic University of Norway for analysis on a QuAatro Autoanalyzer (SEAL Analytical Ltd, Wrexham, United Kingdom).

4.6 Particulate organic carbon / nitrogen and their stable isotopic $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ compositions.

- Samples for POC/PON should be prepared for analysis by acidifying in fuming hydrochloric acid for ca. 12 hours before packing into tin capsules.
- After fumigation and packing, samples will be sent to Vrije Univeriteit, Brussels, Belgium for measurement with an element analyzer (EA, Eurovector, Italy) coupled to an isotope ratio mass spectrometer (Horizon IRMS, Nu Instruments, United Kingdom).

4.7 Chlorophyll *a*

- Chl *a* samples can be processed on ship using a Turner Trilogy Fluorometer (Turner Designs, USA) following the steps outlined below.
- Turn fluorometer on at least 10 min and allow samples to warm to room temperature before taking first measurement.
- Fill 10 mm cuvette with methanol and dry on the outside with a KimTech wipe, place in cuvette holder inside the fluorometer and take measurement. This is the pre-analysis blank measurement.
- After taking first blank, transfer sample into a new 10 mm cuvette and dry on the outside with a KimTech wipe. Place in fluorometer and take measurement. Read the value and note down as Rb value (before acid addition). If sample is too concentrated dilute with methanol, making sure to note down dilution.
- Take the cuvette out of the fluorometer and add 2-3 drops of 5% HCl, cover the cuvette with parafilm and mix gently by inverting 3 times. Wait 30 seconds to allow reaction to complete and take a new measurement. This is the Ra value (after acid addition).
- Take measurements in this way for all samples, and then take a final blank measurement.
- Dispose sample after readings into designated methanol waste container.
- Fluorometer should be calibrated before or after the cruise with Chl *a* extract to derive calibration constants noted down for calculation of Chl *a* and phaeopigments on Excel.

4.8 Biogenic silica

- Samples for the determination of the biogenic and lithogenic silica should be stored and shipped to the University of Brest, France for analysis following the NaOH/HF digestion method of de Master (1981).

4.9 Phytoplankton taxonomy

- Samples for taxonomic analysis should be stored and shipped to the Institute of Oceanology, Poland using light microscopy.
- Samples should be sedimented for 20-40 hours before analysis following the Utermohl method.
- Taxa identification should be done based on morphological characteristics following e.g., Johansen and Fryxell (1985), Thomas (1997), Scott and Marchant (2005), and the online repository at the World Register of Marine Species (<https://www.marinespecies.org/index.php>).

4.10 Flow cytometry

- Samples for flow cytometry should be stored and shipped to UiT the Arctic University of Norway for analysis and retrieval of bacterial (HNA and LNA), pico- and nanophytoplankton abundances using a flow cytometer.

4.11 Net community production using O₂ optodes

- Optode incubation data will be stored on the associated computer and should be backed up on at least one other location. No other processing is required.

4.12 DMSP

- Pre-label glass storage bottles before starting sample preparation.
- DMSP: From each amber bottle, pipette very accurately (!) 10 mL into a 20 mL DMSP-vial with a 10 mL plastic pipet and a red pipetting balloon. You do not need to change pipettes for every sample (save the environment!!), but can use one pipet for all samples of one sampling day. In between each sample: rinse with milli-Q, followed by a few mL of the next sample.
- Add 50 µL of a 2.3µM D3-DMSP working solution.
- Add a pellet of NaOH and close firmly with a screw cap (wearing lab gloves improves the grip on the caps!).
- store at -20°C.

4.13 Particulate organic carbon – ^{13}C .

- Samples for production analysis will be sent to the University of Groningen for analyses with Cavity Ring-Down Spectroscopy analyser (CM-CRDS, with a G2101-I Analyzer, Picarro, California, USA).